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Deliverable D.C3.4

Spent Convictions Scheme: Steps of the legal analysis

By Mira Stammers

Independent research report commissioned by the Australian Criminal
Intelligence Commission (NCIS Pilot Program)

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Acronyms

ACIC	Australian Criminal Intelligence Commission
CbD	Compliance by Design
CtD	Compliance through Design
D2D CRC	Data to Decisions Cooperative Research Centre

Executive Summary

Legislation relating to spent convictions in Australia is complex and inconsistent. Other than Victoria, which does not have a legislated spent conviction scheme, each jurisdiction has a different legislative regime to determine whether a conviction becomes hidden from public view after a set period of time. The multifaceted and varying nature of these jurisdictional regimes weighs heavily on government resources. Currently, Australian police agencies and accredited bodies manually screen criminal records data and making decisions about whether to disclose spent convictions. During 2016-2017, 4.74 million checks were processed, of which 1.42 million were sent for further analysis. Importantly, automated technical solutions using Compliance through Design (CtD) modelling has the possibility of unburdening government agencies of this time-consuming responsibility. To demonstrate a proof of concept on Compliance through Design modelling, a sample use case was analysed, and legal analysis steps were determined. These steps were then used to form the basis of the computational modelling. This deliverable provides an overview of the steps of the legal analysis.

1 Introduction

Generally, information about a criminal conviction in a court of law will be recorded and the criminal conviction remains part of a person's record unless the conviction is overturned, quashed or annulled. Not allowing a person to escape the burden of convictions in the past was deemed unfair by Australian authorities and as impacting negatively in the rehabilitation of criminals.¹ As a result, they, like many other countries,² introduced spent conviction schemes in different States and Territories and at a Commonwealth level.

A "spent conviction" is a conviction which becomes hidden from public view after a set period of time. In jurisdictions where spent conviction schemes exist, the extent to which criminal records may be accessed and/or disclosed is generally limited in relation to older records relating to less serious crimes³. This limitation generally does not apply in relation to convictions for sexual offences or in circumstances where the person has re-offended during the specified waiting period⁴. Whilst the regimes differ, each regime has exemptions which permit the lawful disclosure of spent convictions in certain limited circumstances. These exemptions usually relate to employment in particularly sensitive fields (e.g., police, teachers, childcare workers)⁵. In this sense, unless an ex-offender falls within an exemption, spent conviction schemes operate to encourage the rehabilitation of ex-offenders and to reduce the potential for ongoing punishment or discrimination against them⁶.

Given that Australian criminal law is regulated primarily by each State and Territory, the Commonwealth and each State and Territory have their own spent conviction legislation.⁷ The exception is Victoria that regulates general spent

¹ Australian Human Rights Commission, *Human Rights: One the record: Discrimination in Employment on Basis of Criminal Record* (December 2004)

<<https://www.humanrights.gov.au/publications/human-rights-record-discrimination-employment-basis-criminal-record-under-ahrc-act>>;

Liberty Victoria's Rights Advocacy Project, *A Legislated Spent Convictions Scheme for Victoria: Recommendations for Reform* (May 2017)

<<https://libertyvictoria.org.au/sites/default/files/RAP-report-A-Legislated-Spent-Convictions-Scheme-for-Victoria-Recommendations-for-Reform-20170517.pdf>>.

² Jeanette Knowler, 'Living down the past – spent convictions schemes in Australia' (1994) *Privacy Law and Policy Reporter* 80.

³ Moira Paterson and Bronwyn Naylor, 'Australian Spent Convictions Reform: A Contextual Analysis' (2011) 34 *UNSW Law Journal* 939.

⁴ Paula Gerber and Katie O'Byrne, 'Should Gay Men Still be Labelled Criminals?' (2013) 38(2) *Alternative Law Journal* 84.

⁵ Bronwyn Naylor, 'Do Not Pass Go: The impact of criminal record checks on employment in Australia' (2005) 30(4) *Alternative Law Journal* 177.

⁶ Helen Lam and Mark Harcourt, 'The Use of Criminal Record in Employment Decisions: The Rights of Ex-offenders, Employers and the Public' (2003) 47 *Journal of Business Ethics* 237.

⁷ Commonwealth: Part VIIC of the *Crimes Act 1914* (Cth); New South Wales: *Criminal Records Act 1991* (NSW); Queensland: *Criminal Law (Rehabilitation of Offenders) Act 1986* (Qld); Australian Capital Territory: *Spent Convictions Act 2000* (ACT); Northern Territory:

convictions through a Victoria Police information release policy rather than a law.⁸ Thus, the Victorian administrative scheme operates merely to restrict disclosure rather than to confer legally enforceable rights or obligations⁹.

Exchanges of criminal records data among the jurisdictions in Australia are coordinated by and through the Australian Criminal Intelligence Commission (ACIC). It manages the processes and provides the system through which Australian police agencies and accredited bodies submit nationally coordinated criminal history checks. However, the extensive number of checks is directly linked to the complexity of the regime and inconsistencies among the different jurisdictional schemes. For instance, between 2016 and 2017, the service was used by 244 accredited agencies and 4.75 million checks were processed. This is an exponential increase from the 2.3 million checks conducted just ten years earlier between 2006-2007¹⁰. Almost a third of these checks were then referred to police agencies for further assessment to determine whether the information is disclosable in line with their spent convictions legislation and/or information release policies.¹¹

It is clear that the volume and complexity of these checks cannot be handled efficiently by humans, especially where the majority of questions would not necessarily be complex. As such, an automated solution is warranted to support compliance with spent conviction rules.

In order to demonstrate the viability of an automated solution (via CtD modelling), it was necessary to first complete a use case legal analysis. The use case was selected by the Australian Criminal Intelligence Commission (ACIC) and provided to the Data to Decisions Cooperative Research Centre (D2D CRC) for this purpose. It is outlined below at Table 1.

As the originating and coordinating jurisdictions of the use case is federal, the legal analysis required a review and application of the Commonwealth legislation pertaining to spent convictions. This deliverable identifies the steps to be followed to analyse the provisions contained in (i) Pt VIIC of the *Crimes Act 1914* (Cth) (the "Act") and (ii) Regulations 7A, 8 and Schedule 4 of the *Crimes Regulations 1990*

Criminal Records (Spent Convictions) Act 1992 (NT); South Australia: *Spent Convictions Act 2009* (SA) ; Tasmania: *Annulled Convictions Act 2003* (Tas); Western Australia: *Spent Convictions Act 1988* (WA).

8. Victoria Police, *Information Sheet - Information Release Policy* (September 2017) <https://www.police.vic.gov.au/content.asp?Document_ID=692>. See also the specific scheme for historical homosexual convictions (expungement) in Part 8 of the *Sentencing Act 1991* (Vic).

⁹ Moira Paterson, 'Criminal Records, Spent Convictions and Privacy: A Trans-Tasman Comparison' (2011) 69 *New Zealand Law Review* 84.

¹⁰ Bronwyn Naylor, Moira Paterson and Marilyn Pittard, 'In the shadow of a Criminal Record: Proposing a Just Model of Criminal Record Employment Checks' (2008) 32 *Melbourne University Law Review* 172.

¹¹ Australian Criminal Intelligence Commission, *Criminal History Checks* <<https://www.acic.gov.au/criminal-history-checks>>.

(Cth) (the “Regulations”). It was designed to demonstrate the steps one would follow in determining whether a conviction is spent and/or whether it should be disclosed. The CtD modelling therefore replicates the human decision-making steps via an automated platform.

The work presented in this document has been made in the context of Project C, “Compliance by Design (CbD) and Compliance through Design (CtD) solutions to support automated information sharing”, within the Law and Policy Program, Data to (D2D CRC).

2 Legal Analysis: Five steps for interpreting the Spent Convictions regulation

To demonstrate a proof of concept on CtD modelling, it is necessary to first review the selected use case and determine the applicable steps of the legal analysis. The selected use case is outlined below at Table 1.

Table 1: Person A Use Case

Purpose	Vetting for an appointment as a management consultant to the Australian Federal Police
Coordinating jurisdiction (CJ)	Federal
Originating jurisdiction of Police History Information (PHI)	Federal
PHI	Insider trading (s 1043A(1) of the Corporations Act 2001 (Cth) (2 charges); convicted on 10 August 1998 Released on entering a good behaviour bond for 2 years.

It must be noted that other use cases will produce different, and sometimes additional, steps in the legal analysis and thus the modelling. Whilst the analysis for each use case is unique, this use case forms the basis for establishing a basic legal semantic workflow which may be expanded upon at a later date.

The legal analysis is completed through a series of steps. The steps are outlined below.

Step 1 – Has there been a conviction?

Whilst the use case states that Person A has been convicted of insider trading, it is important to determine whether Person A’s conviction meets the definition of ‘conviction’ within the meaning of the Part.

Section 85ZM(1) of Div 1 of Pt VIIC of the Act defines the meaning of ‘conviction’ to be one where:

- a) the person has been convicted, whether summarily or on indictment, of the offence;
- b) the person has been charged with, and found guilty of, the offence but discharged without conviction; or
- c) the person has not been found guilty of the offence, but a court has taken it into account in passing sentence on the person for another offence.

The facts indicate that the first test is met. Person A was convicted of insider trading, and thus Section 85ZM(1)(a) applies. It is unnecessary to determine whether insider trading is a summary or indictable offence, as this subsection applies to both categories of offences.

Step 2 – Is the conviction spent?

The second step is to determine whether the conviction has been ‘spent’.

Section 85ZM(2) of Div 1 of Pt VIIC of the Act defines a ‘spent conviction’ to be one where:

- a) the person has been granted a pardon for a reason other than that the person was wrongly convicted of the offence; or
- b) the person was not sentenced to imprisonment for the offence, or was not sentenced to imprisonment for the offence for more than 30 months, and the waiting period for the offence has ended.

As Person A has not been granted a pardon, the applicable test falls under Section 85ZM(2)(b). This requires two separate elements to be met, namely:

1. Was there no sentence of imprisonment, or otherwise a sentence of imprisonment 30 months or less?; and
2. Has the waiting period for the offence ended?

The factual matrix indicates that Person A was not imprisoned. Therefore, the first element is met.

Section 85ZL of Div 1 of Pt VIIC of the Act defines the “waiting period” as:

- a) if the person convicted of the offence was dealt with as a minor in relation to the conviction—the period of 5 years beginning on the day on which the person was convicted of the offence; or
- b) in any other case—the period of 10 years beginning on the day on which the person was convicted of the offence.

Person A was convicted on 10 August 1998. We do not know the age of Person A, but in any event, the maximum waiting period has been served, being 10 years. Thus, Person A meets the requirements of having a ‘spent conviction’.

If the conviction had been between five and ten years old, it would be necessary to also determine whether Person A had been dealt with as a minor in relation to the conviction.

As the analysis has confirmed that Person A has a spent conviction, Section 85ZV of Div 3 of Pt VIIC of the Act applies. Broadly, Section 85ZV provides that, subject to Division 6 of Pt VIIC but despite any other Commonwealth, State or Territory law, a person is not required to disclose the fact of a spent conviction to any person, for any purpose.

As this provision is subject to Division 6 of Pt VIIC of the Act which provides for exceptions, each exception must be reviewed.

Step 3 – Do any Division 6 Exclusions apply?

The next step in the legal analysis is to review Div 6 of Pt VIIC of the Act to determine whether the spent conviction falls within one of the exceptions under the Act.

As Person A seeks to be appointed as a management consultant to the Australian Federal Police, the relevant exception is found under Section 85ZZH(a)(ii) of Subdivision B which permits disclosure of spent convictions to law enforcement agencies. The definition of “law enforcement agencies” includes the Australian Federal Police.

Section 85ZZH states:

Division 3 does not apply in relation to the disclosure of information to or by, or the taking into account of information by a person or body referred to in one of the following paragraphs for the purpose specified in relation to the person or body:

(a) a law enforcement agency, for the purpose of making decisions in relation to prosecution or sentencing or of assessing:

(i) prospective employees or prospective members of the agency; or

(ii) persons proposed to be engaged as consultants to, or to perform services for, the agency or a member of the agency;’

“law enforcement agency” is defined under Section 85ZL (Interpretation of Part) and includes under subsection (a), the Australian Federal Police.

Accordingly, whilst the conviction is spent, Section 85ZZH(a) of Div 3 of Pt VIIC of the Act which permits disclosure of spent convictions to law enforcement agencies does not apply.

In conclusion, disclosure to the Australian Federal Police for the purpose of assessing whether Person A should be engaged as a consultant to the Australian Federal Police is permitted.

Additional matters to consider throughout the legal analysis.

It is important to note that Section 85ZP(2) of the Act specifically excludes body corporates from being considered 'a person convicted of an offence'. Thus, spent conviction provisions under the Act do not apply to any use case relating to a body corporate.

Additionally, Section 85ZP(3) of the Act confirms that other than in relation to disclosure to the Federal Court of Australia for the purposes of indictable primary proceedings, criminal appeal proceedings or related matters, disclosure or taking into account a conviction is not authorised by the Act if to do so would contravene any Commonwealth, State, Territory or foreign law. This is an important conflict of laws point that should be considered for each use case and potentially should form an additional step in every legal analysis.

3 Conclusions

The legal analysis demonstrates that Person A's conviction qualifies as a "spent" conviction within the meaning of the Act, but that irrespective of its status, it is required to be disclosed given that Person A is applying to be appointed as a management consultant to a law enforcement agency. Thus, it falls within an exclusion under the regime.

The importance of this analysis is that it identifies a series of steps to be taken in relation to determining whether Person A's conviction is spent and/or needs to be disclosed. These steps were then used to form the basis of the CtD modelling.

Whilst the steps for this specific use case are clear, it is evident that the analysis requires considered decisions to be made at every step. An incorrect decision at any one of the steps could result in either a spent conviction being disclosed when it should not have been, or worse, a spent conviction not being disclosed when it should have been. By automating these solutions, not only is there a significant benefit in terms of time and resources, but the accuracy of the decision-making is likely to increase.

4 References

A. Articles, Books and Reports

Bronwyn Naylor, 'Do Not Pass Go: The impact of criminal record checks on employment in Australia' (2005) 30(4) *Alternative Law Journal*.

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B. Legislation

Annulled Convictions Act 2003 (Tas).

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Spent Convictions Act 2000 (ACT).

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C. Other Sources

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